

D1.3 - Patients, caregivers; and support and clinical organisational needs <WP1 Y1Q2-Q3>

Task leader: Maccabi Healthcare services

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Executive Summary

The process of identifying, diagnosing, treating and caring of elderly people suffering from Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) or Mild Dementia (MD) is complex and involves many actors working together towards a shared goal. This document analyses the needs of the participants of this process, i.e. patients, care providers and caregivers, while accounting for subtleties relating to MCI and MD clusters. Moreover, this document lays the foundation for defining the list of requirements of the DECI system design by describing the actions that should be taken to address aforementioned needs. We also take a step forward by rating the actions from most desired to less important or less relevant.

1 Introduction

This document, along with D1.5: *Design of the final pilot based on the pre pilot study*, is an outcome of Task 1.3: *Deep analysis of patient needs and caregiver requirements in each cluster associated to the assistance, support and care needs, one of the four tasks that comprise Work Package 1 (WP1) of DECI: Analysis of existing models for managing elderly people with cognitive impairment and of their needs.*

Task 1.3 aims to analyse the needs described in previous deliverables and specify the needs and requirements for treatment of patients with cognitive decline from MCI to mild Dementia condition.

These needs and requirements will be composed from the various elements: patient treatment, patient support, informal caregiver support, professional caregiver requirements (healthcare and non-healthcare caregiver) and organizational needs (information security, suiting organization logics and workflows etc.). Therefore, it is important to analyse and identify all relevant needs that will subsequently be validated during solution design activities in order to develop the most adaptive and comprehensive solution. The suggested solution will be examined using the four pilot study models to ensure the adaptively of the system to existing care models and workflows.

This task takes as an input the work carried out in tasks 1.1 and tasks 1.2. Deliverable D1.2: *Patient clusters*, the main outcome of Task 1.2, defines the clusters of patients that will benefit from the use of the system and includes a preliminary analysis of the target population in the different pilot sites. On the other hand, Deliverable D1.1: *State-of-the-art of clinical and assistance management models and practices of older adults with cognitive impairment due to MCI or dementia*, carries out a thorough analysis of the care models in the four DECI pilot sites, describes the strengths and weaknesses within each care model as well as the barriers and facilitators that might have an influence on the implementation of innovative solutions for improving the care of the patients described in Task 1.2.

Most user-centred Human-computer interaction (HCI) methodologies aim to propose methodologies for eliciting the requirements of new interactive systems. Scenario-based design is a family of techniques in which the use of a future system is concretely described at an early point in the development process [1].

Figure 1 depicts the information flow from D1.1 and D1.2, where the target population of DECI was analysed and specified for each pilot site, to D1.3 that analyse the needs form a

patient, caregiver and professional perspective. This result will feed Local Brainstorming Sessions (LBSs) that are participative discussions with stakeholder involved in the care process for patients with MCI or mild dementia, aimed at identify the DECI scenarios (bottom-up perspective, from which the use-cases are generated to serve as the basis for the system design (D1.5).

Figure 1 Methodological approach of T1.3 “Deep analysis of patient needs and caregiver requirements in each cluster associated to the assistance, support and care needs”

One of the challenges within the DECI project is to design a system that can be adapted to different country\regional settings and workflows and support users at all stages of the disease, aims to improve the quality of life of elderly people affected by CI, treating and managing diseases and, in general, supporting the adoption of a healthy and independent lifestyle to the maximum extent.

As detailed in previous deliverables, within four different countries -Israel, Italy, Spain and Sweden- the treatment is provided according to the accepted clinical guidelines, however, there is a difference in the ways of care delivery. For example, Israel has high level of digital infrastructure and most of the care provided for MCI patients by community healthcare organizations while in Italy and Spain the delivery is done mainly through Hospital. Furthermore, there is a difference in the tools used to assess, identify and follow-up of the patients. For example, In Israel, the identification of MCI patients is done using proactive methodology relying on the central medical record and risk

assessment while in other countries it is more reactive. Therefore the system will have to support the different workflows and clinical methodologies to ensure easy adoption in the various sites.

The present deliverable will describe the needs of the various actors in each site as a result of the previous deliverables and will analyse the common and specific needs in each site to produce scenarios and list of requirements for the design of the DECI system.

The methodology used within this document includes:

1. Patient Journey scenario: This section describes the “Patient Journey scenario”. A narrative of **current practice** that synthesizes actors, themes, relationships, and artefacts discovered in the field work [1];
2. List of stakeholders and **actors** participating in the scenario;
3. List of **needs and actions** taken to satisfy said needs with respect to patient, care provider, caregiver and organizational needs.

2 The current Patient Journeys for people with MCI and mild Dementia

The four different settings in the pilot country site will serve as the basis for definition of the DECI care model. From the research performed in D1.1 and D1.2 we concluded that the needs in all four countries as well as those described in the literature are similar. We assume that analysing the different care models and workflows as a basis and design a solution that can be adaptive for these four sites will produce an adaptive solution that will address the identified gaps and problems and can be easily implemented in many care organizations worldwide.

Despite the differences among the care models in the four pilot settings, the patient journey is similar in all settings, going from pre-diagnosis to the diagnosis and the patient having to start the treatment and to cope with their new life situation. In [2], Samsi and Manthorpe analyse different dementia care pathways in different settings, and outline four common points along dementia care pathways found in the literature:

1. **Early symptom identification and first service encounters.** Early symptom identification can be carried out by the person with suspected symptoms or their relatives (in most cases) or by proactive screening programs such as the 75th-

birthday screening program carried out in Maccabi. Most people's first point of call when seeking for help is the primary care physician.

2. **Assessment process.** A common next step along a dementia care pathway is referral from primary care for more specialized assessment and treatment. A full diagnosis can be carried out by a specialist in the Hospital (such as in Getafe) or by a Memory Assessment Unit.
3. **Diagnostic disclosure and communication.** The manner in which a diagnosis of dementia is communicated to the patient and the support offered at this time may be crucial in how people cope with the condition long-term.
4. **Postdiagnostic support.** Postdiagnostic support, as described along a dementia care pathway, depends upon the specific diagnosis and the stage of dementia. There have been concerns that people with MCI often receive no support and are simply asked to return in a year's time to a memory service or if symptoms appear to worsen.

In their study "The 'patient journey' for people with Alzheimer's Disease: Exploring early signs and diagnosis' [3], the Alzheimer's Society and Lilly UK explored the patient journey for people with Alzheimer's disease and their caregivers in the UK, beginning with noticing symptoms and leading to the diagnostic and treatment processes experienced. [3] describes 4 main key points:

1. Noticing symptoms and presenting to a doctor.
2. Referral to a specialist or memory clinic.
3. Diagnosis and treatment.
4. Emotion and coping styles.

Within the present document, we have identified four common steps that are part of the patient journey in the four pilot settings, and that are relatable to the patient journey models found in the literature. **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** 2 resents an overview of the 4 phases:

Figure 2. Common patient journey for people with MCI and dementia

1. **Detection of MCI or Dementia symptoms.** As mentioned beforehand, early identification of symptoms can be carried out in a reactive (i.e. the users themselves or the family caregivers) or proactive, through screening programs. When a person is suspected to have symptoms of cognitive decline beyond normal ageing, they usually ask for an appointment with their primary care physician, who is responsible for their general care.
2. **Assessment and diagnosis.** If the physician in primary care detects signs of cognitive impairment, they usually refer patients to specialized services for a full diagnosis.
3. **Treatment and care plan.** Once the diagnosis has been established, it is time to start with the treatment, both pharmacological and non-pharmacological.
4. **Follow-up.** After the diagnosis and the treatment have been established, patients and caregivers go back to their everyday lives. It is common that no specific follow-up strategy is established, keeping a regular visit schedule every 6 months or 1 year, or visiting the primary care physician in case of deterioration.

The following diagrams describe the **current** patient journey at every pilot site, consisting of the four phases described above:

2.1 Israel

Figure 3. Patient journey diagram for Israeli pilot site

2.2 Spain

Figure 4. Patient journey diagram for Spanish pilot site

2.3 Italy

Figure 5. Patient journey diagram for Italian pilot site

2.4 Sweden

Figure 6. Patient journey diagram for Swedish pilot site

2.5 Combined over all pilot sites

This diagram summarizes the commonalities among the different pilot site along the stages of the patient journey:

Figure 7. Combined patient journey diagram for all pilot sites

3 Stakeholders and actors along the patient journey at every pilot site

In this section we list the stakeholders for whom we have mapped the needs. These are the actors participating in the Patient Journey in every pilot site.

3.1 Israel

Stakeholders along the patient journey at MAC

1. Detection
 - Patients
 - Informal caregivers (usually family members)
 - General Practitioner
 - Nurse
 - Home care teams
2. Diagnosis and Assessment
 - Geriatrician
 - Occupational Therapist
3. Treatment
 - Occupational therapist
 - Geriatrician
 - Social worker
 - Home care teams
 - Nurse
 - Physiotherapist
 - Dietician
 - Psychologist/Neuropsychologist
4. Follow up
 - General Practitioner
 - Nurse
 - Occupational therapist
 - Geriatrician
 - Social worker
 - Home care teams
 - Physiotherapist
 - Dietician
 - Psychologist/Neuropsychologist

3.2 Spain

Stakeholders along the patient journey at HUG

1. Noticing symptoms and first service encounters
 - Patients
 - Informal caregivers (usually family members)
 - General Practitioner
 - Nurses in Primary Care
2. Assessment and diagnosis
 - Specialist (Geriatrician, Neurologist or Psychiatrist)
 - Special services, such as Imaging Services.
 - Neuropsychologist (only for special cases on the edge)
3. Treatment and care plan
 - Specialist (Geriatrician, Neurologist or Psychiatrist)
 - Social worker
 - External services, such as the Centre for the Prevention of Cognitive Decline of the Municipality or Research Foundations (not included in the 'official' care pathway)
4. Follow-up. There is no standardized care pathway after the patient has been diagnosed. The patient will have scheduled revisions every 6 months – 1 year with the specialist, and can visit their GP on demand.

3.3 Italy

Stakeholders along the patient journey in FDG

1. Detection
 - Patients
 - Informal caregivers (usually family members)
 - General Practitioner
 - Other Clinical Specialists
 - Physicians of in-patient services
2. Diagnosis and Assessment
 - Geriatrician
 - Neuropsychologist
3. Treatment
 - Geriatrician
 - Social worker
 - Nurse

- Physiotherapist
- Occupational therapist
- Psychologist/Neuropsychologist
- Educator
- Health and Social care assistants

3.4 Sweden

Stakeholders along the patient journey at VGR

1. Detection
 - Patients
 - Informal caregivers (usually family members)
 - General Practitioner
 - Other Clinical Specialists
 - Physicians of in-patient services
 - Managers from all care providers
2. Diagnosis and Assessment
 - Geriatrician
 - Neuropsychologist
 - General Practitioner
 - Managers from all care providers
 - Occupational Therapist
 - Dementia Nurse
3. Treatment
 - Geriatrician
 - Social worker
 - Nurse
 - Physiotherapist
 - Occupational therapist
 - Psychologist/Neuropsychologist
 - Health and Social care assistants
 - Managers from all care providers

4 Mapping Needs and Actions

A preliminary taxonomy of needs, reported in the Annex, was developed as an input for the Local Brainstorming Sessions, where each country developed a first analysis of needs. From this preliminary analysis of needs, added to previous results of the project (D1.1, D1.2, D2.1) we constructed a spreadsheet mapping the needs of the patients, healthcare professionals, caregivers and organizational needs, in order to define a comprehensive taxonomy of needs coherent with the specific DECI project goals.

Every need is addressed by a set of actions/services performed today in the present care model described above. In furtherance of designing the DECI system, every site has analysed and rated¹ the top desired needs and activities as they pertain to their different clusters of MCI and MD and to the workflows at every site, as shown below in table 1.

From this table the most important needs and actions will be extracted to yield the system requirements; functional and non-functional for the design of the system.

¹ Rating in the table is based upon the results of the D1.2 population analysis, the CCW and the LBS. A scale of 1 to 5 rates the perceived importance of an item. With a score of "5" corresponding to an action or need which is most important, while a score of "0" reflects that the item is not pertinent to MCI/Dementia or was considered out of the scope of the DECI project (this is the case for example of the scores "0" given by FDG for the items detection and clinical diagnosis).

No	Need category	Need	Action to address the need	MAC		HUG		FDG		VGR		MCI		Dementia	
				MCI	MD	MCI	MD	MCI	MD	MCI	MD	total	AVG	total	AVG
1	Detection	Patient detection	Reactive detection	4			4	0	0	5	4	9	3	8	2.667
2			Proactive search I (Database parameters)	4			4	0	0	5	3	9	3	7	2.333
3			Proactive search II (75 th birthday)	4			0	0	0	4	3	8	2.667	3	1
4	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical	Clinical diagnosis	5			5	0	0	5	5	15	3.75	10	3.333
5	Diagnosis and assessment		Overall medical condition	5			5	5	5	4	5	19	4.75	15	5
6	Diagnosis and assessment		Medical instability	0			3	0	0	0	4	3	0.75	8	2.667
7	Diagnosis and assessment	Psychological	Behavior and mood	5			5	5	5	5	5	20	5	10	5
8	Diagnosis and assessment		Anosognosia	0			2	1	1	0	0	3	0.75	3	1
9	Diagnosis and assessment	Physical	Assess the Risk of malnutrition	5			5	5	5	3	5	18	4.5	15	5
10	Diagnosis and assessment	Functional	ADL	5			5	5	5	3	5	18	4.5	15	5

11	Diagnosis and assessment		risk for falls	5		5	5	5	5	3	5	18	4.5	15	5
12	Diagnosis and assessment		Frailty	5		5	5	5	5	4	4	19	4.75	14	4.667
13	Diagnosis and assessment	Socio economic	Assess Socio economic state	5		5	5			5	4	15	5	9	4.5
14	Diagnosis and assessment	Caregiver burden	Assess Caregiver burden	5		5	5	5	5	2	4	17	4.25	14	4.667
15	Patient environmental needs	The person might not have an adequate and appropriate home	Assuring suitable living space	1		1	2	0	0	4	4	6	1.5	6	2
16	Patient environmental needs	The person might have problems keeping their home tidy and organized	Assuring maintenance of living space	3				3	5	2	3	8	2.667	8	4
17	Patient environmental needs	Buy food	Shopping assistant	2		3		3	4	2	4	10	2.5	8	4

18	Patient environmental needs	Eat in a safe way	Malnutrition avoidance	2		4		3	5	2	3	11	2.75	8	4
19	Patient environmental needs	Patients not able to keep track of their expenses	Money budgeting	3		2	1	3	5	3	4	11	2.75	10	3.333
20	Patient environmental needs	Caring for someone else	Caring for someone else	1		0	0	1	0	4	4	6	1.5	4	1.333
21	Patient environmental needs	Wandering expose people to dangers	tracking / prevent wandering	0		1	3	0	4	0	0	1	0.25	7	2.333
22	Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	Information about the disease, symptoms and evolution	4		5	5	1	0	4	4	14	3.5	9	3
23	Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a	Information on current condition and treatment	4		5	5	2	2	4	4	15	3.75	11	3.667

		language they can understand													
24	Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	The patient can contact a health professional for questioning	4		3	3	0	0	5	5	12	3	8	2.667
25	Patient physical needs	People might need support for designing a physical activity plan	Physical activity plan and exercise	4		5	5	2	1	4	4	15	3.75	10	3.333
26	Patient physical needs	Drugs (chronic disease management)	Education on side-effects on medication treatment by clinical pharmacologist or clinical team coordinated by case manager	4		4	4	0	0	4	4	12	3	8	2.667

27	Patient physical needs	Have a prescription by general practitioner	Medication plan	4		4	4	5	5	4	4	17	4.25	13	4.333
28	Patient physical needs	Remember timing and drugs according to prescriptions	Medication Reminders	4		4	4	5	5	4	5	17	4.25	14	4.667
29	Patient physical needs	Eyesight/ hearing/ Communication		0				3	2	2	2	5	1.667	4	2
30	Patient physical needs	People can have high risk of fall	Fall detection	3		3	4	3	5	3	4	12	3	13	4.333
31	Patient physical needs	People need to be able to move	Immobility detection	3		3	3	3	5	3	4	12	3	12	4
32	Patient physical needs	Keeping neat and tidy	education, follow-up	2		2	2	3	5	2	2	9	2.25	9	3
33	Patient physical needs	Continence		0		1	1	1	4	0	3	2	0.5	8	2.667

34	Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Access to non-pharmacological treatment	4		4	5	5	5	4	5	17	4.25	15	5
35	Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Alternative treatments	4		4	4	3	3	4	4	15	3.75	11	3.667
36	Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Brief psychotherapies	4		4	4	0	0	4	3	12	3	7	2.333

37	Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Psychopharmacological treatment	0		0	0	0	0	3	3	3	0.75	3	1
38	Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Remote monitoring of psychological status	4		5	5	2	2	3	3	14	3.5	10	3.333
39	Patient psychological needs	People might need help in daily activities that imply memory functions	Cognitive stimulation	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5

40	Patient psychological needs	People might need help in daily activities that imply memory functions	Online Cognitive Training	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5
41	Patient psychological needs	Alcohol abuse prevention	Alcohol abuse prevention	3		3	3	3	0	3	3	12	3	6	2
42	Patient psychological needs	inadvertent self-harm		1		1	1	0	1	0	0	2	0.5	2	0.667
43	Patient psychological needs	deliberate self-harm		0				0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.5
44	Patient psychological needs	Psychotic symptoms	Monitoring hallucinations or delusions	0		3	4	3	4	4	4	10	2.5	12	4

45	Patient Social needs	Patient refuses help and sociality outside home / lives alone in an isolated hose / does not have partners	social interaction	0		3	3	3	3	3	3	9	2.25	9	3
46	Patient Social needs	Intimate relationship		0		0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.25	1	0.333
47	Patient Social needs	The person might not have relatives / friends / etc. With whom realising social activities	Recommendation of social activities	1		2	2	1	2	3	4	7	1.75	8	2.667

48	Patient Social needs	People with cognitive problems might have problems with other people that might take advantage of their condition (i.e. using their money)	Abuse/Neglect prevention	1		1	2	0	2	2	2	4	1	6	2
49	Patient general needs	People might not be aware of available social services	information of the social benefits available in the area	4		4	4	3	4	4	4	15	3.75	12	4
50	Patient general needs	People are not able to contact social services or social workers	Patients can contact the social worker	4		4	4	2	0	5	5	15	3.75	9	3
51	Patient general needs	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)	4		4	4	2	0	4	4	14	3.5	8	2.667

52	Patient general needs	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Discuss financial and long-term care plans	4		4	4	1	0	4	4	13	3.25	8	2.667
53	Clinical team needs	Coordinated care	Coordination of care	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5
54	Clinical team needs	Information sharing	Clinical team information sharing	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5
55	Clinical team needs	Improve diagnosis method	Improve diagnosis method	5		5	5	*	*	5	5	15	5	10	5
56	Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Advising on deciding course of action	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5
57	Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5
58	Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Standardized care pathway	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5

59	Clinical team needs	Accessibility	Facilitating access to medical services in rural/ isolated areas	3		2	3	0	0	5	5	10	2.5	8	2.667
60	Clinical team needs	Longitudinal treatment	comprehensive treatment of multiple training sessions and group therapy+ follow-up	5		5	5	3	3	5	5	18	4.5	13	4.333
61	Social care team needs	Information sharing	Health team information sharing (including social care)	4		4	4	5	5	4	4	17	4.25	13	4.333
62	Social care team needs	Information sharing	To improve social awareness about the disease	4		5	5	3	3	5	5	17	4.25	13	4.333
63	Social care team needs	Information sharing	To inform general population, health professionals and relatives about the available social resources	4		5	5	5	5	5	5	19	4.75	15	5
64	Social care team needs	Accessibility	To facilitate access to social services in rural/ isolated areas	3		3	3	0	0	4	4	10	2.5	7	2.333

65	Social care team needs	Accessibility	To facilitate and to speed up access to social services (Day Centres, Night Centres, etc.)	3		3	3	5	5	3	4	14	3.5	12	4
66	Follow up	People could need help in daily life activities that imply memory functions	Online Cognitive Training	5		5		3	3	5	5	18	4.5	8	4
67	Follow up	People could need help in daily life activities that imply memory functions	Monitoring of cognitive condition	5		5		3	3	5	5	18	4.5	8	4
68	Follow up	overall condition	monitoring overall condition	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5
69	Follow up	Remember timing and drugs according to prescriptions / ensure adherence	measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5

70	Follow up	social care	Assess timely changes evolving needs for social care support	5		5	5	5	5	5	5	20	5	15	5
71	Organizational needs														
72	Caregivers needs	Physical and psychological monitoring of the caregiver	Interventions with the caregiver	4		4	4	5	5	5	5	18	4.5	14	4.667
73	Caregivers needs	Medical information for NFC	Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease	4		5	5	5	5	4	4	18	4.5	14	4.667
74	Caregivers needs	Medical information for NFC	Information about the secondary effects of medication	4		4	4	3	3	4	4	15	3.75	11	3.667
75	Caregivers needs	Communication healthcare prof. - NFC	The caregiver can ask questions to the health professional	4		3	3	5	5	4	4	16	4	12	4
76	Caregivers needs	Social care information for NFC	Information about available social services in the area	4		4	4	5	5	4	4	17	4.25	13	4.333

77	Caregivers needs	Social care information for NFC	Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)	4		4	4	3	3			11	3.667	7	3.5
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Table 1 – Needs and Actions

5 Conclusions

In this document we have mapped the needs of the patients, care providers and caregivers with respect to the detection, diagnosis and assessment, treatment and follow up of both MCI and mild Dementia patients. Along with D1.5: *Design of the final pilot based on the pre pilot study* which will describe the pilot parameters, desired DECI scenarios and the DECI patient journeys, it constitutes the completion of Task 1.3.

With describing the actions required to fulfill the needs and rating them according to relevance and importance we have taken a leap forward towards defining the requirements and specification to be addressed in WP3 *Design of the Digital Environment for Cognitive Inclusion*, under Task 3.3 *Definition of requirements and design of ICT infrastructure and application*. These requirements and specification will be determined after considering top rated actions and establishing a cutoff for lower scores in consideration of the required development to achieve such features in the final design of the DECI system. The design of the DECI system, which will be carried out in WP3, will take inspiration from the DECI Patient Journeys illustrated in this document, the DECI patient journeys and desired DECI scenarios illustrated in D1.5. It will rely on the commonalities in processes and approaches while allowing for adjustments according to idiosyncrasies of the different sites.

6 References

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7 Annex - Preliminary taxonomy of needs

In order to ensure that the solutions proposed by DECI will fulfil the goals of all stakeholders involved in the care process of older adults with different levels of cognitive impairment, the DECI project has adopted a user-centred approach, involving different stakeholders since the early stages of the development process. Around month 5 of the project, the four pilot sites organized a set of co-creation workshops (CCWs) that focused on eliciting the current status of care of people with cognitive impairment, the gaps and the possible solutions that might help fill these gaps. The results of the CCWs were used to complete Deliverable D1.1: *State-of-the-art of clinical and management models and practices of elderly patients with MCI*.

Later, around month 9 of the project, each pilot site organized a Brainstorming Sessions involving different stakeholders involved in the care of older adults with cognitive impairment. While the CCWs focused on the care process and its gaps from a general point of view, the brainstorming sessions focused on how the technologies available within the DECI project might help meet the needs of all actors involved along the ‘patient journey’ of older adults with cognitive impairment. In preparation for the local brainstorming process are elements coming from CCWs and knowledge generated from other project tasks, including a description of the tackled care process, of the targeted population segments and the needs per population segment.

7.1 Patient needs

Task 1.2 of DECI, named *Definition of patient clusters based on the intensity of the pathology and condition and life style*, focused on the identification of specific characteristics and features of patients involved in the pilot project of each clinical implementation. The main outcome of task 1.2 was deliverable D1.2: Patient clusters. D1.2 defined the target population of the DECI project, by giving the general definitions and specifying the inclusion/exclusion criteria, the relevant dimensions, variables and tests that will be used to analyse the target population in the different pilot sites. For what concerns the assessment of needs of patients, D1.2 proposed the use of the Camberwell Assessment of

Need for the Elderly (CANE²), a comprehensive, person-centred needs assessment tool that has been designed for use with older people. The different areas of the CANE-S have been used as a basis to identify and classify the needs of patients with different stages of Cognitive Impairment.

Table 2. Unmet patient needs, based on the CANE-S

Need category	Needs example
Accommodation	Architectural Barriers No neighbours Dangerous neighbourhood Dangerous furnishings and electric devices Windows without protection at high floors
Food/Eating	Buy food Store food Prepare meals Eat in a safe way
Looking after home	Does the person have difficulty looking after their home? How much help does the person receive from relatives and friends looking after their home? Does the person receive any help from local services for looking after their home?
Self-care	Are people able to keep themselves tidy or appropriately dress? Is the person able to keep up with instrumental daily activities such as dressing, bathing or making laundry?
Caring for someone else	Does the person have difficulty caring for someone else?

² Reynolds, T., Thornicroft, G., Abas, M., Woods, B., Hoe, J., Leese, M., & Orrell, M. (2000). Camberwell assessment of need for the elderly (CANE) development, validity and reliability. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 176(5), 444-452

Daytime activities	<p>Does the person have adequate social, work, leisure activities?</p> <p>Living according to their own habits, desires and behavioural changes dementia related</p> <p>Walking inside and outside home</p> <p>Sleeping</p>
Memory	<p>People could need help in daily activities that imply memory functions (call someone by phone, remember where clothes are, spending money, learning new procedure, etc.)</p> <p>Other</p>
Eyesight / hearing / communication	<p>People need help if they have limited vision or hear functions: read newspaper or books, read instructions, hear someone speaking, hear TV/music player or other devices</p> <p>People can have limitations in comprehension or in verbal communication</p>
Mobility / Falls	<p>People need to walk inside / outside</p> <p>People can have high risk to get lost when outside</p> <p>People can have high risk to get lost when outside</p> <p>If they live alone, they can have high risk of falling in solitude</p>
Contenance	<p>People have to stay clean</p> <p>People cannot be able to use diaper</p> <p>People could not be able to reach toilet in time</p>
Physical Health	<p>Is the person receiving any medical interventions besides those related to CI?</p> <p>Are other comorbidities treated properly?</p>
Drugs	<p>Have a prescription by general practitioner</p> <p>Shop medicines</p> <p>Store drugs in a right way (expiries, temperature, humidity)</p>

	<p>Use medicines in a right way, alone or needing help (blister, cps, vials, inhalators, etc.)</p> <p>Remember timing and drugs according to prescription</p> <p>Communicate benefits and side effects</p> <p>Remember new prescriptions</p>
Psychotic Symptoms	Does the person have symptoms such as delusional beliefs, hallucinations, formal thought disorder or passivity?
Information on condition and treatment	<p>People need to receive and understand the information about their condition and treatment.</p> <p>People have to mean their own conditions and the meaning of therapies prescribed.</p> <p>People could not remember what physicians or nurses say.</p> <p>People could not understand what physicians or nurses write.</p> <p>People could not be able to read according to eyesight loss or cognitive limitations.</p> <p>People could not learn new information, as is where looking for new information.</p>
Psychological distress	<p>Confusing accommodation or relations</p> <p>Daily life distressing</p> <p>Boring life or poor sociability</p> <p>Poor ability to cope</p>
Deliberate self-harm	Is the person a danger to themselves?
Inadvertent self-harm	<p>Risk of fall</p> <p>Risk of death</p> <p>Risk of intoxication related to mistakes in eating or drinking toxic substances inside home (bleach, other poisons) or assuming drugs (overdose)</p> <p>Risk of domestic accidents</p>
Abuse / Neglect	Dementia patients cannot remember the value of their money

	<p>Persons with dementia might not recognize people or confuse strangers for relatives or friends</p> <p>Persons with dementia without a legal representative could not control their own budget, with high risk of economic substractions</p>
Behaviour	<p>Patients do not remember to take antipsychotics or are not able to have drugs</p> <p>Wandering expose people to dangers</p> <p>Behavioural problems overwhelm caregiver tolerance</p> <p>Patient do not want to be helped</p> <p>Sadness, apathy</p>
Alcohol	<p>Does the person drink excessively or have a problem controlling their drinking?</p>
Company	<p>The person lives alone in an isolated house</p> <p>The person has behavioural problems</p> <p>The person refuses help and sociality outside home</p>
Intimate relationships	<p>Does the person have a partner, relative or friend with whom they have a close emotional/physical relationship?</p>
Money / Budgeting	<p>People might have problems for buying essential items and/or paying bills independently</p> <p>People might be</p>
Benefits	<p>People are not able to activate social services and social benefits</p> <p>People are not able to contact social services or social workers</p> <p>The person does not want to contact social services</p> <p>The person does not have a legal attorney</p>

7.2 Caregiver needs

Feelings of loss and anxiety (Need for better caregiver operative support)
The informal caregiver can suffer from mood alterations in different stages of the disease
The informal caregiver can oversee symptoms of the evolution of the disease
The informal caregiver can confound attitudes of normal ageing with worsening symptoms
The informal caregiver can confound secondary effects of the medication with worsening symptoms
The informal caregiver might not be aware of the available social services in the area
The informal caregiver might not get enough information about the legal aspects of the disease
The informal caregiver might suffer from social and economic problems due to the disease of their dear ones
Better activity management and handover, when multiple caregivers are involved

7.3 Professional needs

Healthcare provision
Better coordination between Primary Care and Specialized Care
Train GPs to diagnose and treat MCI
Reduce time between suspicion and diagnosis
Multidisciplinary team of specialists
Named 'case manager' (possibly consider the patient as self-case manager)
Continued, Integrated Care
Improve the overall care model
Agreed care plan

Care plan based on patient's needs
Comprehensive care plan, including aspects such as nutrition, physical activity and occupational therapy
Medication management
Standardized care pathway (Streamline the care process, reducing inefficiencies and time-consuming activities that do not directly impact the patient's quality of life, creating a Smart Set for Geriatrics)
Humanization of care ('Too focus on my illness, too Little focus on my health')
Improved diagnosis method
Screening of vulnerable population
Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies
Social care
Better coordination between Healthcare and Social Care (possibly by nurse)
Shortage of social care activities / support
To improve social awareness about the disease
To inform general population, health professionals and relatives about the available social resources
To facilitate access to social services in rural / isolated areas
To facilitate and to speed up access to social services (Day Centres, Night Centres, etc.)